

ISic1498

I.Sicily inscription 1498

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido, sep.104

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3573

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μ(άρκος) Ἀντώνιος
2. Σκόρπος Κορίν
3. θιος ἐνθάδε κίτ
4. αι ἐτῶν κε χαίρετε
5. οἱ προσιόντες
- 6.

Apparatus

Text of Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

Marcus Antonius Skorpus the Korinthian lies here, 25 years old. Farewell, those present.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493851

EDCS 38200009

PHI 313640

PHI 331792

Bibliography

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